

1 ***Phyllocoptes parviflori* is a distinct species and a vector of the pervasive blackberry leaf**
2 **mottle associated virus**

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4 Tobiasz Druciarek^{1,2}, Andrea Sierra-Mejia¹, Stanislaw K. Zagrodzki^{1,2}, Shivani Singh¹, Thien
5 Ho³, Mariusz Lewandowski^{1,2*} and Ioannis E. Tzanetakis^{1*}

6
7 ¹Department of Entomology and Plant Pathology, Division of Agriculture, University of
8 Arkansas System Fayetteville, Arkansas, United States 72701

9 ²Section of Applied Entomology, Department of Plant Protection, Institute of Horticultural
10 Sciences, Warsaw University of Life Sciences–SGGW, Nowoursynowska 159, 02-776
11 Warsaw, Poland.

12 ³Driscoll's Inc., Watsonville, CA 95076, USA

13
14 *Corresponding authors: mariusz_lewandowski@sggw.edu.pl (Mariusz Lewandowski) and
15 itzaneta@uark.edu (Ioannis E. Tzanetakis)

16
17 Present/permanent address: Tobiasz Druciarek, Stanislaw K. Zagrodzki and Mariusz
18 Lewandowski – Section of Applied Entomology, Department of Plant Protection, Institute of
19 Horticultural Sciences, Warsaw University of Life Sciences–SGGW, Nowoursynowska 159,
20 02-776 Warsaw, Poland.

21
22 **Abstract**

23 Several viruses are transmitted by eriophyid mites (Acariformes: Eriophyoidea) including
24 blackberry leaf mottle-associated emaravirus (BLMaV) (*Emaravirus rubi*). BLMaV is
25 transmitted by an unidentified eriophyid species and is involved in blackberry yellow vein, a
26 devastating disease in the southeastern United States. In this study, we assessed the eriophyid
27 mite *Phyllocoptes parviflori* as a vector of BLMaV and clarified its taxonomic status as it was
28 previously synonymized with *Phyllocoptes gracilis*. *P. parviflori* can efficiently transmit
29 BLMaV. The virus was found to cause yellow vein disease symptoms on 'Ouachita'
30 blackberry marking a paradigm shift as disease symptoms have always been associated with
31 multiple virus infections. Therefore, we propose renaming the virus to blackberry leaf mottle
32 virus. The occurrence of *P. parviflori* on wild and cultivated blackberries, as well as its ability
33 to colonize other *Rubus* species, enhances its importance as a major contributor to the spread
34 of yellow vein disease.

36 Key words: eriophyid, transmission, blackberry leaf mottle associated virus

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38 **1. Introduction**

39 Eriophyids (Acariformes: Eriophyoidea) are phytophagous arthropods that feed on all plant
40 parts except roots. Many species are economically significant as pests and virus vectors.

41 Several viruses are transmitted by eriophyid mites, with the most extensively studied being
42 members of the genera *Rymovirus* and *Tritimovirus* (family *Potyviridae*), *Allexivirus* (family
43 *Alphaflexiviridae*) (de Lillo and Skoracka, 2010) and *Emaravirus* (family *Fimoviridae*, order
44 *Bunyavirales*), the focus of this communication.

45 Two emaraviruses, blackberry leaf mottle-associated emaravirus (BLMaV) (*Emaravirus*
46 *rubi*) and raspberry leaf blotch emaravirus (RLBV) (*Emaravirus idaeobati*), have been
47 identified in *Rubus*, leading to significant losses in blackberry and raspberry production,
48 respectively (Hassan et al., 2017; McGavin et al., 2012). BLMaV, along with other viruses
49 cause blackberry yellow vein disease (BYVD), the most economically significant viral
50 disease of blackberry in the southeastern United States. BYVD affects fruit quality and yield,
51 resulting in yellowing of the main veins, mottling, oak leaf patterns, and chlorotic ringspots.
52 The disease reduces yield and can render infected plants unproductive in as few as five years
53 (Hassan et al., 2017; Martin et al., 2013a). Hassan et al. (2017) determined that the virus can
54 be transmitted by unidentified eriophyid species, highlighting the importance of this finding
55 for the management of BYVD.

56 RLBV was discovered in Europe in raspberry plants exhibiting symptoms of leaf blotch
57 disorder. The disease was reported for the first time some 100 years ago and attributed to
58 feeding damage caused by *Phyllocoptes gracilis* (Masee, 1931). However, we now know that
59 the disease is caused by RLBV and although there have not been conventional transmission
60 experiments, observations suggest that *P. gracilis* is a vector (McGavin et al., 2012).

61 *Phyllocoptes gracilis* has been reported in Europe, North America, and Asia, and is
62 considered as a common species across a wide range of hosts (Breakey, 1945; Kuang, 1995;
63 Nalepa, 1890). Breakey (1945) initially observed this species on red raspberry in the United
64 States, and this was confirmed by H.H. Keifer. However, a few years earlier the second author
65 described two closely related species: *Phyllocoptes calirubi* Keifer, 1938 from blackberry,
66 and *Phyllocoptes parviflori* Keifer, 1939, from thimbleberry and salmonberry (Keifer, 1938,
67 1939). In 1952, *P. parviflori* was synonymized with *P. gracilis* due to similarities in main
68 morphological features and their shared habitat (Keifer, 1952). Later Jeppson et al. (1975)
69 characterized *P. parviflori* as a variable species in terms of morphological features but no
70 further research was conducted to clarify this conundrum.

71 We investigated the taxonomic status of *P. gracilis* and *P. parviflori* and determined
72 that they are two distinct species. In addition, we assessed the competence of *P. parviflori* as a
73 vector of BLMaV and estimated the transmission efficiencies through single and multiple
74 mite transfers.

75

76 **2. Material and methods**

77 **2.1. Sample collection and morphological analyses**

78 Eriophyid-infested leaves samples were collected from raspberry (*Rubus idaeus* L.) in Poland
79 (five locations), Czechia (one location) and the United States (three locations; Supplemental
80 Table 1). Material was examined for the presence of *P. gracilis* under a dissecting
81 stereomicroscope. Similarly, eriophyid-infested leaves from blackberry (*Rubus* subg. *Rubus*
82 Watson) were sampled and examined for *P. parviflori* and *P. calirubi*. The most important
83 morphological traits commonly used in eriophyid species descriptions (Lewandowski et al.,
84 2014; Valenzano et al., 2020) were compared using data from the original descriptions. All
85 measurements were done on a Soft Imaging System Cell D connected to the camera and a

86 phase-contrast Olympus BX51 microscope (Shinjuku, Tokyo, Japan). For mite transmission,
87 *R. fruticosus* blackberry from Watsonville (California, USA), naturally infested with *P.*
88 *parviflori* and BLMaV-positive, were used as the mite source (Supplemental Table 1). To
89 verify the purity of the *P. parviflori* colony, 50 specimens were slide-mounted in a modified
90 Berlese medium (Amrine and Manson, 1996) for phase-contrast microscopic examination.
91 Moreover, ten mites from each plant were DNA-barcoded (Druciarek et al., 2019). All
92 examined specimens are deposited as slide-mounted material in the Mite Collection of the
93 Institute of Horticultural Sciences, Department of Plant Protection, Section of Applied
94 Entomology, Warsaw University of Life Sciences, Warsaw, Poland. According to (Liu et al.,
95 2017), the collection is named WULS.

96

97 **2.2. Molecular data and phylogenetic analyses**

98 Specimens from each population were also placed in 0.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes containing
99 5 μ L of RNase-free water and used for molecular analyses. Transcripts of the cytochrome c
100 oxidase subunit I (COI, mtDNA), D2 region in 28S and ITS1 of ribosomal DNA (D2, 28S
101 and ITS1 rDNA) were amplified from single specimens using direct RT-PCR (Druciarek et
102 al., 2019). Primers used for amplification and sequencing are shown in Supplementary table 2.
103 Amplicons were Sanger-sequenced bidirectionally at Macrogen Inc. All sequences of
104 *Phyllocoptes* have been deposited in GenBank (Supplemental Table 1).

105 Datasets containing 573 bp fragments for COI (mtDNA) and 604 bp for D2 (28S
106 rDNA), were analyzed in Mega X (Kumar et al., 2018) unless otherwise stated. Sequences of
107 *Leipothrix juniperensis* (GenBank MZ274920 and MZ289016), like the three species of
108 *Phyllocoptes* discussed here - belonging to the Phyllocoptinae, Phyllocoptini, were used as the
109 outgroups for both datasets.

110 The COI and D2 sequences were aligned separately by ClustalW (Thompson et al.,
111 1994) using default weighting parameters. Analyses of the pairwise genetic distances between
112 and within nucleotide sequences, as well as the choice of the most appropriate evolutionary
113 models for estimation of inter- and intra-lineage genetic variation were performed using
114 MEGA X (Kumar et al., 2018). The Tamura-Nei model with γ distribution (TN93 + G)
115 (Tamura and Nei, 1993) was applied to the COI dataset, and Tamura 3-parameter model with
116 a γ distribution (T92 + G) (Tamura, 1992) to the D2 dataset. Standard error estimates were
117 obtained by a 1000 bootstrap pseudo-replicates.

118 Phylogenetic relationships for studied fragments were reconstructed using Maximum
119 Likelihood (ML) and Bayesian Inference (BI). Models for both datasets were selected using
120 jModelTest v.2.1.1 (Darriba et al., 2012) based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)
121 and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) likelihood scores for 88 different models. The GTR
122 + I + G model (Tavaré, 1986) was applied to COI and HKY + G model (Hasegawa et al.,
123 1985) to D2 datasets. To perform the Bayesian Inference (BI) combined analysis of COI, D2
124 fragments, the sequence files were concatenated in a single matrix in Mesquite v.3.0.4
125 (<http://www.mesquiteproject.org>). Bayesian analyses were performed in MrBayes v.3.2.6
126 (Ronquist et al., 2012). Two independent runs were executed for each dataset using four
127 Markov chains (three heated and one cold) run for ten million generations, with trees sampled
128 every 1000 generations. The analysis was performed until the average split deviation was
129 below 0.01, and 25% of trees obtained at the beginning were excluded as burnin. Obtained
130 trees were edited with FigTree v.1.4.4 (<http://tree.bio.ed.ac.uk/software/figtree/>).

131

132 **2.3. Transmission**

133 Mite-free black raspberry (*Rubus occidentalis* 'Munger') and blackberry (*Rubus fruticosus*
134 'Ouachita') plants obtained from North American Plants, Inc nursery (USA) were used in two

135 independent transmission experiments. Plants were pruned a week before mite transfer to
136 force new growth and potted in 7.5 cm diameter pots. BLMaV-free status of the plants was
137 verified prior to transmission studies (data not shown). Total nucleic acids were extracted
138 from plant tissues and reverse transcribed according to procedures described by Poudel et al.
139 (2013). PCR targeting separately the NADH dehydrogenase β -subunit (an internal control
140 ensuring the quality of nucleic acids) and the virus RNA 3 were performed (Hassan et al.,
141 2017). Amplicons were Sanger sequenced bidirectionally at Macrogen Inc. Moreover,
142 BLMaV-positive 'Ouachita' blackberry, obtained in transmission studies, was subjected to
143 HTS, and analyzed *in silico* using VirFind (Ho and Tzanetakis, 2014) to verify its single
144 infection status, essentially as described (Villamor et al., 2022). HTS revealed the presence of
145 blackberry virus F, an intergrating badnavirus (Shahid et al., 2017) within the sample. The
146 BVF presence was further investigated using primers designed to amplify both the reference
147 genome (Shahid et al., 2017) and the HTS virus sequence (Supplemental Table 2). To
148 determine whether BVF was present in the integrated or episomal form rolling circle
149 amplification (RCA) and PCR/RT-PCR were performed. For PCR and RT-PCR aliquots of
150 total nucleic acid from ten plants positive for BLMaV were respectively digested with RNase
151 (4U of RNase T1, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and DNase (4U of Turbo DNase, Thermo Fisher
152 Scientific) for two hours before used as template for amplification (Supplemental Figure 3).

153 Adult mites were used in all transmission experiments. They were collected under a
154 dissecting microscope with the use of an eyelash tool (human eyelash attached to a dissecting
155 needle) and transferred onto test plants. In the first experiment, vector competence was
156 checked using five viruliferous mites moved to each of the 20 black raspberry plants. In the
157 second experiment, one or five viruliferous mites were moved to blackberry test plants, 20
158 plants in each combination. Plants were covered with plastic (PET) cylindrical cages as

159 described (Druciarek et al., 2023) and arranged in a randomized complete block design. A
160 month later plants were tested for BLMaV as described above.

161

162 **3. Results**

163 **3.1. The reinstatement of *Phyllocoptes parviflori* Keifer, 1939 (locus typicus: USA, 164 **California)****

165 Several morphological characteristics distinguish eriophyid mites from the United States
166 when compared to *P. gracilis* collected in Europe. The most important qualitative characters
167 are prodorsal shield ornamentation and microtubercles on the dorsal annuli. Specimens from
168 the US have a more complex pattern of lines on the prodorsal shield compared to *P. gracilis*,
169 and oval microtubercles located near the margin of annuli. Mites from Europe also have
170 pointed micro tubercles located on the rear margin of annuli (Fig. 1). Both characters are also
171 helpful for the distinction from another eriophyid species occurring on blackberries in the US,
172 *P. calirubi* (Fig. 1). From quantitative characters, the most distinct are the number of dorsal
173 annuli, length of scapular setae (*sc*), *c2* and *c3* (Table 1). Supplementary description of *P.*
174 *parviflori* is shown in supplementary file 1. The morphological distinction of *P. parviflori*
175 from *P. gracilis* was also supported by analyses of two molecular markers, COI (mtDNA) and
176 D2 (28S rDNA).

177 The final datasets consisted of 49 aligned sequences of COI (573 bp): 3 of *P. calirubi*,
178 17 of *P. gracilis*, 28 of *P. parviflori* and 1 of outgroup; and 51 sequences of the D2 (604 bp):
179 4, 17, 29 and 1, respectively. For several mite specimens only one marker was obtained (see
180 Supplementary Table 1) which resulted in a larger number of distinct concatenated sequences
181 than of either COI or D2 sequences. In the alignments, 182 (31.8%) sites were parsimony
182 informative, 236 (41.2%) variable for COI; 55 (9.1 %) sites were parsimony informative, and
183 143 (23.7%) variable for D2. General topologies of the phylogenetic trees inferred by

184 Bayesian inference (BI) and maximum likelihood (ML) analyses revealed similar structures,
185 thus, only the BI trees are presented in Figure 2. The data strongly support the monophyly of
186 the genus *Phyllocoptes*, as well as that of *P. gracilis* and *P. parviflori* (Fig 2 and
187 supplementary Fig. 1 and 2). Both species were clustered separately, whereas *P. calirubi* and
188 *P. gracilis* group in the same sub-clade (Fig. 2). Similar tree topology, with equally strong
189 support to separate *P. parviflori* and *P. gracilis*, were constructed based on the D2 dataset
190 (Supplementary Fig. 1). However, for COI, *P. calirubi* is basal to *P. parviflori* and *P. gracilis*,
191 whereas in the D2 and concatenated COI+D2 trees, *P. calirubi* forms a sister clade to *P.*
192 *gracilis* (Fig. 2, Supplementary Fig. 2). COI variation among these two populations was
193 28.0% (SE=3.0%), while D2 divergence between *P. parviflori* and *P. gracilis* was 5.9%
194 (SE=1.1%), and *P. parviflori* and *P. calirubi* were 7.3 (SE=1.3%). A pairwise comparison of
195 both markers' distances is provided in Table 2.

196

197 **3.2. Transmission**

198 One of the 20 black raspberry 'Munger' infested with five *P. parviflori* individuals tested
199 positive for BLMaV. Efficiency was higher on 'Ouachita' blackberry; with single mite-
200 transfers reaching 35% transmission. When increasing the number of mites to five
201 individuals, efficiency increased to 70% (Table 3) as verified by sequencing of all PCR
202 amplicons. HTS analysis showed 279,536 virus-specific reads for BLMaV that represented
203 99% of the virus genome and nine reads (76 bp each) for Blackberry virus F (BVF) that
204 mapped to five regions of the genome, with one region of 124 bp mapping five of the total
205 reads. The nucleotide identity of these reads with the BVF reference genome in GenBank was
206 between 80% to 91%. Previously designed detection primers (Shahid et al., 2017) failed to
207 yield any amplicon; however, amplicons of the expected size were obtained with the primers
208 designed in this study. RCA was unsuccessful possibly due to inhibitors, similar to what

209 observed in the virus characterization study (Shahid et al., 2017). PCR using the RNase-
210 digested samples yielded amplicons for BVF in all samples, whereas RT-PCR in DNase-
211 digested samples yielded faint amplicons in three out of the ten samples (Supplemental Figure
212 3) with at least seven samples that are not infected with the episomal form of the virus. The
213 approach used suggests that BVF is integrated within the 'Ouachita' genome and symptoms
214 can solely be caused by BLMaV and are typical of BYVD (Fig. 3; Martin et al., 2013b).

215

216 **4. Discussion**

217 Mites have been linked to several devastating diseases. However, only recently has the
218 scientific community begun to realize the full extent of the species involved in transmission.
219 Plant virus-transmitting mites mainly belong to the genus *Brevipalpus* (flat mites) and a
220 limited genera of eriophyid mites, such as *Aceria*, *Cecidophyopsis*, *Phytoptus*, and
221 *Phyllocoptes* (Bragard et al., 2013). This study extends the list of confirmed eriophyid vectors
222 to *P. parviflori* and indicates that the virus can by itself cause BYVD symptoms on
223 'Ouachita', a paradigm shift as the disease has been associated previously with multiple virus
224 infections. For this reason, we propose that the common name of the virus is changed to
225 blackberry leaf mottle virus (BLMV).

226 It is important to note that based on the findings of Hassan et al. (2017), *P. parviflori* is
227 not the only vector of this virus, as the authors used a different, unidentified species to
228 successfully transmit the virus. Transmission of an emaravirus with multiple eriophyid
229 species has recently been reported by Druciarek et al. (2023). Multiple vectors increase the
230 risk of virus spread and further complicates the epidemiology of the disease. According to
231 Hassan et al. (2017), BLMV vector may play a crucial role in BYVD epidemiology by
232 transmitting the virus between cultivated and wild blackberries that act as natural reservoirs
233 for the virus.

234 Our study demonstrates that an individual *P. parviflori* mite could transmit BLMV.
235 However, when multiple mites were used, transmission efficiency reached 70%, a high
236 number when compared to other eriophyid transmission studies (Seifers et al., 1997; Kulkarni
237 et al., 2002; Di Bello et al., 2018; Druciarek et al., 2023). We observed low BLMV
238 transmission efficiency on black raspberry (*R. occidentalis* 'Munger'), with only one out of 20
239 plants infected in five mites-transfer experiment. Nevertheless, this result demonstrates that *P.*
240 *parviflori* can move BLMV between different *Rubus* species. BLMV has been detected in
241 numerous cultivated and wild blackberries (Hassan et al., 2017b; Hassan and Tzanetakis,
242 2019). However, it is important to note that the virus is highly underreported, and there are no
243 surveys to clearly demonstrate its true distribution. The successful graft transmission onto
244 black raspberry 'Munger' plants, as confirmed by Hassan et al. (2017), aligns with our
245 findings of raspberry as a suitable host, and also show that *P. parviflori* can feed on raspberry
246 plants for a time sufficient to acquire and transmit the virus. The lower efficiency of
247 transmission compared to blackberry 'Ouchita' plants may result from the mite preference for
248 a specific host or the adaptation costs. BLMV has only been reported naturally infecting
249 blackberry (Hassan et al., 2017b; Hassan and Tzanetakis, 2019); whereas the vector of the
250 virus was initially observed on *Rubus parviflorus* (*Rubus* subg. *Anoplobatus*), commonly
251 known as thimbleberry (Keifer, 1939) and later identified on cultivated and wild blackberries
252 during these studies.

253 Eriophyid mites, as highly specialized plant feeders, may incur adaptation costs when
254 they colonize a new plant species, as demonstrated for *A. tosichella* (Laska et al., 2021;
255 Skoracka et al., 2022). Populations of *P. parviflori* used in our experiments originated from
256 blackberries, and their transfer to black raspberry plants could potentially reduce the fitness of
257 mites, ultimately lowering the efficiency of transmission. It should be emphasized that the
258 presence of *P. parviflori* on wild and cultivated blackberries and their ability to colonize other

259 *Rubus* species significantly increases the species' importance as a key factor responsible for
260 the spread of BYVD. Other potential hosts, *e.g.*, thimbleberry and wild *Rubus* species should
261 be screened for both, the vector and BLMV. Undoubtedly, there is an urgent need for further
262 studies on the BLMV-*P. parviflori* pathosystem, as disease management should include other
263 strategies (control of alternate hosts and targeting the virus vector) in addition to the use of
264 virus-tested propagation material.

265 The considerable reduction and simplification in the body plan of eriophyid mites
266 necessitates the use of structures from all parts of the body and appendages for their
267 systematic classification. However, these structures are scarce (Lindquist and Amrine, 1996),
268 which can lead to mistakes when describing a new species, as in the case of *P. parviflori*. The
269 species has been noted only in the United States (Keifer, 1939). However, its occurrence and
270 host range remains unclear due to its prior synonymization with *P. gracilis* (Keifer, 1952), a
271 species commonly found in Europe on raspberry plants (Boczek, 1961; Denizhan et al., 2015;
272 Nalepa, 1890; Roivainen, 1950, 1947), but also reported in the United States (Breakey, 1945).
273 Phylogenetic analysis shows the unjustified nature of synonymization. The genetic distance in
274 the COI marker ranged from 28.0% to 39.3%, and in the D2 marker ranged from 5.9% to
275 7.3%, confirmed that three *Phyllocoptes* species commonly found on blackberry plants are
276 distinct. Similar or lower genetic distances using these markers have been observed in the
277 differentiation of *Phyllocoptes* species on rose (Druciarek et al., 2021), cryptic speciation
278 among lineages of *A. tosichella* (Skoracka et al., 2013) or *Trisetacus* species inhabiting
279 coniferous plants (Lewandowski et al., 2014). The reinstatement of *P. parviflori* is also
280 supported by the examination of quantitative and qualitative morphological characters of *P.*
281 *parviflori*, *P. gracilis*, as well as the third species occurring on blackberries, *P. calirubi*. One
282 of the most useful quantitative features is the ornamentation of the prodorsal shield, which can
283 be easily analyzed on slide-mounted specimens. This character is commonly employed for

284 species identification and is considered one of the most important on the species level (de
285 Lillo et al., 2010; Lindquist and Amrine, 1996). Identification based on quantitative characters
286 can be further supported by comparing the number of dorsal annuli and measuring the length
287 of *sc*, *c2*, and *c3* setae. These characters are among 27 features commonly used in the
288 identification of eriophyid species (Lewandowski et al., 2014; Skoracka et al., 2002).

289 Proper identification of species, especially those that are closely related or cryptic, holds
290 significant importance not only in the field of taxonomy and systematics but also in
291 translational research, particularly when dealing with economically important organisms such
292 as *Phyllocoptes* species colonizing crops. The presence of three morphologically similar
293 *Phyllocoptes* species on *Rubus* could further complicate the management of BYVD. Accurate
294 vector identification is crucial to control disease outbreaks and prevent spread to new areas.
295 Furthermore, the findings of this study can serve as a valuable contribution to further research
296 on the ability and efficiency of BLMV transmission and the phylogeny and systematics of
297 *Phyllocoptes* as important virus vectors. These insights can aid in enhancing our
298 understanding of the intricate interactions between vectors and viruses in plant disease
299 dynamics.

300

301 **5. Conclusions**

302 In conclusion, our results demonstrate that *P. parviflori* serves as a vector for the spread of
303 BLMaV among different *Rubus* species. Even a single individual of this mite vector could
304 transmit BLMaV, but the efficiency of transmission increases to 70% when multiple mites are
305 involved. This study expands the list of confirmed eriophyid vectors of viruses to include *P.*
306 *parviflori* and suggests that the virus can independently cause BYVD symptoms on
307 'Ouachita', marking a paradigm shift as the disease has traditionally been associated with
308 multiple virus infections. Therefore, we propose renaming the virus as blackberry leaf mottle

309 virus (BLMV). Phylogenetic analysis supports the distinction between *P. parviflori* and *P.*
310 *gracilis*, invalidating the previous synonymization. This study provides additional information
311 describing *P. parviflori* as a vector for BLMV. The presence of the vector on wild and
312 cultivated blackberries, along with its ability to colonize other *Rubus* species, significantly
313 amplifies its importance as a key factor responsible for the spread of BYVD.

314 **Authorship contribution statement**

315 **Tobiasz Druciarek:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Experimentation,
316 Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Andrea Sierra-Mejia:** Experimentation.
317 **Stanislaw K. Zagrodzki:** Experimentation. **Shivani Singh:** Experimentation. **Thien Ho:**
318 Experimentation. **Mariusz Lewandowski:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis,
319 Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization,
320 Supervision. **Ioannis E. Tzanetakis:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original
321 draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

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328 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

329 Tobiasz Druciarek: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition,
330 Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. Andrea
331 Sierra-Mejia: Investigation, Experimentation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing.
332 Stanislaw K. Zagrodzki: Investigation, Methodology. Shivani Singh: Investigation,
333 Methodology. Thien Ho: Investigation, Methodology. Mariusz Lewandowski:

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334 Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing –
335 original draft, Writing – review & editing. Ioannis E. Tzanetakis: Conceptualization,
336 Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Writing – review & editing.

337 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

338 The authors declare that they do not have any conflicts of interests associated with the
339 research presented here.

340 **Data availability**

341 All sequences of BLMV and eriophyid mites were submitted and available in the GenBank
342 Database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore>).

343

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346

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Table 1. Comparison of female morphological characters of *Phyllocoptes gracilis*, *P. parviflori*, and *P. calirubi*. All measurements are in μm .

Taxonomical traits	<i>P. gracilis</i>		<i>P. parviflori</i>		<i>P. calirubi</i>	
	Nalepa, 1891	Polish populations	Keifer, 1939	USA populations	Keifer, 1938	USA populations
Length of body	120	174-257	170-180	152-249	140-155	187-240
Width of body	38	44-55	-	42-57	47-56	60-68
Length of chelicerae	-	12-16	-	12-16	-	13-15
Length of prod. shield	-	33-38	36	32-40	-	40-48
Width of prodorsal shield	-	33-42	-	32-43	-	46-54
Length of frontal lobe	-	3-4	-	3-5	-	4-6
Length of setae sc	-	17-20	14	12-15	11	9-12
Sc setae tubercle apart	-	17-22	17	16-21	20	18-21
No. of dorsal annuli	80	69-82	65-70	53-70	45-50	47-57
No. of ventral annuli	-	76-96	-	64-87	70-75	68-73
Length of setae c2	-	31-39	9	42-57	5	16-25
Length of setae d	-	45-56	24	33-48	23	41-51
Length of setae e	-	22-28	11	11-17	20	33-41
Length of setae f	-	25-29	22	15-23	24	23-28
Length of genitalia	-	9-12	8	8-12	12.5	11-13
Width of genitalia	-	19-24	18	18-22	20	21-25
Length of setae 3a	-	26-33	14	12-17	9	19-25
Ridges on genital coverflap	-	8-13	10	10-12	10-12	11-13
Length of leg I	-	29-32	30	26-31	28	31-34
Length of tibia I	-	5-6	7	6-8	6.5-7.5	6-8
Length of tarsus I	-	6-8	7	6-7	6.0-6.5	6-8
Rays in empodia I	-	5	5	5	5	5
Length of leg II	-	27-31	27	25-31	27	28-32
Length of tibia II	-	5-6	5	4-6	4.5	4-6
Length of tarsus II	-	7-8	7	6-8	6.5	7-8
Rays in empodia II	-	5	-	5	-	5
Type host	<i>Rubus idaeus</i>		<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>		<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	

Table 2. Estimates of average evolutionary divergence (standard error in parentheses) for the cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 (COI, mtDNA) and D2 subunit (28S rDNA) sequence pairs within and between *Phyllocoptes* species from *Rubus* spp. and *Leipothrix juniperensis* used as the outgroup species.

COI (mtDNA)	<i>P. parviflori</i>	<i>P. gracilis</i>	<i>P. calirubi</i>	outgroup
<i>P. parviflori</i>	0.020 (0.000)			
<i>P. gracilis</i>	0.280 (0.030)	0.030 (0.010)		
<i>P. calirubi</i>	0.393 (0.034)	0.354 (0.042)	0.000 (0.000)	
<i>Leipothrix juniperensis</i>	0.528 (0.062)	0.537 (0.060)	0.430 (0.049)	n/c
D2 (28S rDNA)				
<i>P. parviflori</i>	0.004 (0.002)			
<i>P. gracilis</i>	0.059 (0.011)	0.001 (0.001)		
<i>P. calirubi</i>	0.073 (0.013)	0.070 (0.013)	0.000 (0.000)	
<i>Leipothrix juniperensis</i>	0.295 (0.038)	0.300 (0.038)	0.328 (0.042)	n/c

Table 3. BLMaV transmission efficiency by *Phyllocoptes parviflori*. Plants infected/no. of plants used (% transmission)

Host plant	Single-mite transfer	5-mite transfer
<i>Rubus occidentalis</i> 'Munger'	-	1/20 (5)
<i>Rubus fruticosus</i> 'Ouachita'	7/20 (35)	14/20 (70)

Figure 1. *Phyllocoptes* from *Rubus*, antero-dorsal females: a – *P. gracilis*; b *P. parviflori*; c – *P. calirubi*. A full dorsal view of *P. parviflori*, and other details including the genital plates of both female and male are shown in the Supplementary File 1.

Figure 2. Combined Bayesian inference (BI) analysis tree constructed from the concatenated cytochrome c oxidase subunit I sequences (COI) and 28S r-RNA subunit D2 sequences of *Phyllocoptes* mites collected from *Rubus* plants and the outgroup species (*Leipothrix juniperensis* obtained from GenBank).

A.

B.

Figure 3. Blackberry leaf mottle virus symptoms that are typical of blackberry yellow vein disease. A) Ringspot symptoms B) Vein yellowing and chlorotic feathering pattern.

Supplemental Table 1. Collection data for *Phyllocoptes* spp. from *Rubus* plants located in the USA and Europe.

Taxon name	Locality	Geographical coordinates	Host plant taxon	Date of collection	Sample code	Accession numbers		
						COI	D2	
<i>Phyllocoptes parviflori</i>	US-AR: Rogers	36°20'50"N 94°06'35"W	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	15.05.2019	KZ125	OQ869677	OQ888660	
					KZ126	OQ869678	OQ888661	
					KZ128	OQ869679	OQ888662	
					KZ132	OQ869680	OQ888663	
					KZ124		OQ888659	
					KZ134		OQ888664	
	US-AR: Clarksville	35°31'52"N, 93°24'10"W	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	19.07.2017	s310	OQ869674		
					19.07.2017	s314	OQ869673	
						s317	OQ869676	
						s322	OQ869675	
	US-MO: Ironton	37°34'57"N, 90°37'42"W	<i>Rubus</i> sp. (wild blackberry)	23.04.2022	MLW1221	OQ869655	OQ888636	
	US-AR: Rogers	36°20'50"N 94°06'35"W	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	27.04.2022	MLW1231	OQ869681		
					MLW1233	OQ869682		
	UA-AR: Huntsville	36°07'00"N 93°45'04"W	<i>Rubus</i> sp. (wild blackberry)	01.05.2022	MLW1328		OQ888641	
	US-AR: Fayetteville	36°02'41"N 94°10'15"W	<i>Rubus</i> sp. (wild blackberry)	08.05.2022	MLW1361	OQ869656	OQ888638	
					MLW1362	OQ869657	OQ888639	
					MLW1363	OQ869658	OQ888640	
					MLW1364	OQ869659		
					MLW1370		OQ888637	
	US-CA: Watsonville	36°53'22"N 121°46'03"W	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	17.05.2022	MLW1237	OQ869660	OQ888642	
MLW1238					OQ869661	OQ888643		
MLW1240					OQ869662	OQ888644		
MLW1251					OQ869663	OQ888645		
21.05.2022					MLW1255	OQ869664	OQ888646	
					MLW1260	OQ869665	OQ888647	
					MLW1333		OQ888648	

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					MLW1330	OQ888649
					MLW1331	OQ888650
				23.05.2022	MLW1263	OQ869670 OQ888654
					MLW1265	OQ869672 OQ888656
					MLW1266	OQ869671 OQ888655
					MLW1319	OQ888658
	US-AR: Winslow	35°49'01"N 94°11'24"W	<i>Rubus</i> (wild blackberry)	22.05.2022	MLW1248	OQ869666 OQ888651
					MLW1366	OQ869667 OQ888652
					MLW1367	OQ869669 OQ888653
					MLW1368	OQ869668 OQ888657
<i>Phyllocoptes calirubi</i>	US-MO: Boone Township	38°08'09"N 91°16'52"W	<i>Rubus</i> sp. (wild blackberry)	23.04.2022	MLW1219	OQ869683
					MLW1220	OQ869684
	UA-AR: Huntsville	36°07'00"N 93°45'04"W	<i>Rubus</i> sp. (wild blackberry)	01.05.2022	MLW1325	OQ888666
					MLW1327	OQ888667
					MLW1326	OQ888668
	US-CA: Watsonville	36°53'22"N 121°46'03"W	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	23.05.2022	MLW1323	OQ869685 OQ888665
<i>Phyllocoptes gracilis</i>	EU/CZ: Smrek	50°53'33"N 15°16'01"E	<i>Rubus idaeus</i> (wild raspberry)	07.07.2020	KZ181	OQ869687 OQ888670
					KZ182	OQ869688 OQ888669
					KZ183	OQ869686 OQ888671
	EU/PL: Polesie	52°45'31"N 20°19'23"E	<i>Rubus idaeus</i> (wild raspberry)	01.08.2020	KZ226	OQ869691 OQ888680
					KZ227	OQ869689 OQ888678
					KZ228	OQ869690 OQ888681
				05.10.2020	KZ587	OQ888679
	EU/PL: Michrów	51°56'31"N 20°47'35"E	<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	10.10.2018	KZ1	OQ869692 OQ888675
				01.08.2019	KZ236	OQ869693
					KZ237	OQ869694
				10.07.2020	KZ638	OQ888676
					KZ640	OQ888677
	EU/PL: Kaleń	52°00'41"N 20°42'24"E	<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	18.06.2019	KZ171	OQ869695 OQ888672
					KZ172	OQ888674

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					KZ173	OQ869697	OQ888673
					KZ190	OQ869696	
					KZ191	OQ869698	
	EU/PL: Dąbrowice	51°55'15"N 20°06'14"E	<i>Rubus idaeus</i> (wild raspberry)	20.07.2019	KZ201	OQ869702	OQ888683
					KZ203	OQ869701	OQ888682
	EU/PL: Stóg Izerski	50°53'28"N 15°18'11"E	<i>Rubus idaeus</i> (wild raspberry)	02.07.2020	KZ186	OQ869700	OQ888684
					KZ187		OQ888685
					KZ218	OQ869699	
							ITS1
<i>Phyllocoptes parviflori</i>	US-CA: Watsonville	36°53'22"N 121°46'03"W	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	17.05.2022	MLW1309	OR050588	
					MLW1310	OR050589	
					MLW1311	OR050590	
					MLW1312	OR050591	

Supplemental Table 2. Primers designed for the detection of BVF based on the reference genome and the sequences obtained in high throughput sequencing

Primer name ^a	Sequence
BVF_HTS_tail_4814F	5'-CATCGGAGCAACTACCTGCTGTG-3'
BVF_HTS_tail_5355R	5'- GCAGTCGGCTGAATATCTGGATTGATG-3'
BVF_HTS_tail_6461F	5'- GAGTCGGCTGATTCAAATCTACTACC-3'
BVF_HTS_tail_7457R	5'-ATTGGGCCCCATCGTCACTC-3'

^a primers were designed to align to both the reference BVF genome and the HTS sequence. Due to high diversity 5' adaptors were added to increase the primer length and melting temperature.

Supplementary Figure 1. Bayesian inference (BI) analysis tree constructed using HKY + G model for the 28S rRNA subunit D2 data sequences of *Phyllocoptes* mites collected from *Rubus* plants and the outgroup species (*Leipothrix juniperensis* obtained from GenBank).

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Supplemental Figure 2. Bayesian inference (BI) analysis tree constructed using GTR + I + G model for the cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 (COI) sequences of *Phyllocoptes* mites collected from *Rubus* plants and the outgroup species (*Leipothrix juniperensis* obtained from GenBank).

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Supplemental Figure 3. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) of NADH dehydrogenase β -subunit (NADH- β , expected size ~1300bp (genomic copy), 721bp (transcript)), and blackberry virus F (BVF) using primer set BVF_HTS_tail_4814F and BVF_HTS_tail_5355R (expected size 541 bp).

A) NADH- β PCR M: 100 bp ladder, C-:water control, C+: cDNA BLMaV HTS sample, 1-10: RNase-digested BLMV positive samples; the absence of a 721 bp amplicon suggests only DNA is being amplified.

B) BVF PCR M: 100 bp ladder, C-:water control, C+: cDNA BLMaV HTS sample, 1-10: RNase-digested BLMV positive samples.

C) NADH- β PCR M: 100 bp ladder, C-:water control, C+: cDNA BLMaV HTS sample, 1-10: DNase-digested BLMV positive samples; the absence of amplification suggests complete DNA digestion.

D) NADH- β RT-PCR M: 100 bp ladder, C-:water control, C+: cDNA BLMaV HTS sample, 1-10: DNase-digested BLMV positive samples; the presence of a 721 bp amplicon validates RNA integrity.

E) BVF RT-PCR M: 100 bp ladder, C-:water control, C+: cDNA BLMaV HTS sample, 1-10: DNase digested BLMV positive samples.